

Practice Abstract no. 51

FOODITY - Open Call #2 project - REDUCE

The FOODITY project launched the second of its two open calls in May 2024 and closed in July 2024. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in November 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is "REDUCE: Reduction through Engagement and Data Utilization for Controlling Excess."

Profile

Project acronym / title	REDUCE Reduction through Engagement and Data Utilization for Controlling Excess
Partners (country)	Spritz Matter s.r.l. (Italy), Behavix s.r.l. SB (Italy), TESAF Department of the University of Padova (Italy)
Project area	Services

Context

One out of two food trays contain significant quantities of leftovers at a canteen. Plate waste is typically bound to be thrown away with no chance of recovering. In Italy alone this amount of food leftovers represents ca. 38.000 tonnes of food wasted every year, a quantity that could feed a big stadium with three meals a day for more than a year and represents € 266 million in loss.

The goal of the REDUCE project is to develop a tool to reduce plate waste by combining technology and consumer engagement. Two main reasons drive the need to address the problem starting from the consumption phase:

- **Bullwhip effect reduction:** Preventing food excess, rather than redistributing it, mitigates the bullwhip effect: a supply chain issue where small changes in consumer demand amplify upstream. Addressing user leftovers provides a more accurate understanding of actual demand, positively impacting the supply chain.
- **Behavioural change:** While it is generally unanimous that "wasting food is not good", food wastage is widely present in canteens across the world. This means that the nuances that characterise food waste at user level deserve careful exploration to evaluate how specific interventions can accompany users towards a more virtuous behaviour.

The REDUCE project takes place in a public hospital canteen (Vicenza, Italy) where meals are served to employees on a daily basis. The project consists of three main pillars:

- **Leftovers quantification algorithm** development with a purposely developed Computer Vision device to monitor users plate waste, both from a qualitative and quantitative point of view, in order to assess the current situation and evaluate future improvements.
- **User engagement**, before and after the meal phase, to collect valuable feedback and understand plate waste causes, while fostering the behavioural change towards a more virtuous scenario.
- **Leftovers forecast** algorithm development to correlate different factors, predict food waste generation and prioritise target interventions to reduce food waste.

Objectives

The main objective of the REDUCE project is the development of a platform where catering companies can remotely monitor food wastage occurring in different locations distributed on the territory. Access will be provided to a private area where data will be displayed through customisable dashboards. Data regarding food waste, environmental parameters (e.g. temperature, noise level) and consumers' meals habits will be collected and displayed.

Specific objectives of the project include:

- Verify and confirm reasons for plate waste that have been clustered during previous surveys.
- Identify other reasons that have not been considered and if they can fall under some of the already existing clusters or if new ones are required;
- Verify the frequency with which specific reasons for waste occur and define priority with which they need to be addressed to efficiently tackle food waste;
- Verify the efficacy of the communication material by evaluating user engagement performance (QR scansions) over the total attendance of the canteen;
- Verify how effective the introduction of reward policies can be with regards to user engagement;
- Achieve accuracy improvements of the computer vision software in recognizing and quantifying food; increase speed in food recognition by the computer vision software; increase food categories segmentations that the computer vision software will be able to recognize;
- Design efficient predictive models that correlate appetite and cafeteria menu to users' food waste and meals habits.

Impact

The REDUCE project is expected to demonstrate significant potential in addressing food waste and promoting virtuous eating habits through an innovative use of data-driven technology and active user engagement.

Collective catering in the EU is a significant sector, serving a large and repetitive customer base with standardised menus. It accounts for one-quarter of all out-of-home meals, translating to 6 billion meals annually and reaching 67 million people daily. This presents a major opportunity to address the issue of food waste within this setting, thereby significantly reducing waste and positively influencing the behavior of a considerable population.

Also, reducing plate waste can contribute to mitigating the bullwhip effect by aligning actual consumption with supply, decreasing the need for overproduction and excessive inventory. This leads to a more efficient supply chain, lower costs, and reduced environmental impact.

The overall output is not only a reduction in food waste but a concrete impact over people's lives. The REDUCE project represents a chance to not only foster food waste reduction but also to convey users' habits towards healthier food choices and positive improvements on consumer lives.

